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OBITUARY

IN MEMORIAM

Professor András Nagymarosy
1949-2016

In the present obituary, we would like to pay last honors to Professor Andras Nagymarosy, a distinguished, founding member of the European Ecocycles Society and member of the Editorial Board of its international open access scientific journal ECOCYCLES.

The untimely death of Professor Andras Nagymarosy, Professor at the Eotvos Lorand University, Budapest, Hungary, on October 1, 2016 brought about a tragic loss to both the Hungarian and the international scientific community. Those who knew him will remember him not only for his outstanding performance as a teacher and researcher, but also for his unique, restless personality, seeking continuous challenges. His work included both theoretical and practical features geology, and he paid attention to maintain harmony between these aspects.

His advancement in science, his knowledge, as well as his ability to associate ideas and to draw analogies between seemingly unrelated phenomena impressed everyone who knew him. His competence in overseeing the expanding research activity of the team he was leading and his outstanding working capacity - that even a youngster would admire - gave him deserved fame and reputation.

The topics closest to his heart and the field he studied with perpetual intensity were the historical geology and stratigraphy of Parathetys, nannoplankton micropaleontology, cenozoic geology of the Alpine-Carpathian-Pannonian region.

He graduated from the Eötvös József High School, Budapest, obtained his MSc in geology at the Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, in 1974, and started to

work at the Geological and Geophysical Institute of Hungary, in Budapest.

His academic career was hallmarked as early as 1975 in his paper on the absolute and relative ages of the clay formations at Kiscell, Hungary (Földtani Közlöny 105: p. 188).

In 1977 he joined the Department of Physical and Applied Geology, Eötvös Loránd University as an assistant professor. He soon established research on Paleogene and Neogene geology of Central Europe, the Miocene paleogeography and paleoecology of Western Carpathian - North Pannonian basins with particular emphasis on nannoplankton biostratigraphy, taught courses on historical geology and palaeontology, palaeoclimatology and palaeogeography, obtained his CSc and PhD degrees in earth sciences from the Hungarian Academy of Sciences in 1993, and served as head of the Department of General and Historical Geology between 1994 and 2004.

He summarized his research in 54 publications that were cited in the scientific literature 977 times. Many of the publications he authored are regarded as essential by the scientific community, and his contributions to the monographs *The Mediterranean Basins: Tertiary Extension within the Alpine Orogen* (Durand et. al. 1999) and *The Geology of Hungary* (Haas, J. ed. 2001) drew most pronounced reception. His most prestigious awards are the Széchenyi Professor Award (1997-2003 and 2003-2006); the highest Hungarian government prize, as well as the honorary titles "Excellent Worker of Higher Education" (1978) and the Pro Universitate Gold Medal (2012).

Although Professor Nagymarosy spent his entire career in Hungary, his influence on Tertiary geology, stratigraphy, palaeontology, palaeogeography and the scientific interpretation of the development of Parathetys has been felt throughout the world. The scientific community regarded several of the

publications he authored as essential. He also dealt with the Neogene stratigraphy of the Mediterranean region and visited countries in the area many times. He was also involved in teaching at graduate schools of several universities abroad. Thus, he served as an invited lecturer at the Comenius University in Bratislava, Slovakia, the University of Gothenburg, Sweden, the University of Bergen, Norway, the University of Karlsruhe, Germany and the Vrije University of Amsterdam, the Netherlands. He was an honorary professor at the Karoly Robert University College (Gyöngyös, Hungary).

In the scientific community he played several roles: he was the secretary of the Paleontology Section of the Hungarian Geological Society, president of the Oligocene Subcommittee of the Hungarian Stratigraphic Society, and a member of the Geographical Society of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences.

He was also an expert in the geography, history and culture of ancient Europe, and also of the time following the Napoleonic wars until today.

Professor Nagymarosy will long be remembered by all of his colleagues around the world as an excellent scientist and a great and beloved teacher, a true friend with a warm personality and a polymath who possessed a vast knowledge in all areas of life.

He was a dedicated family man. He and his wife Hajnalka raised and cared for four children, and taught them the value of family, education, arts, and hard work.

Andras Nagymarosy was a multi-talented man - a real "renaissance personality". He worked hard in the laboratory, on the cathedra, and in the field, but he also enjoyed life to the fullest.

Professor Nagymarosy was a wine and beer expert (a founding member and a knight of the Hungarian Wine College).

He was a prefect of the Wine College (Budapest, Hungary), and a lecturer of the Wine & Spirit Education Trust. He investigated the complex relationships between the properties of wine and the geography of its terroir (a term referring to the climate, geomorphology, hydrographic conditions, aspect and soils of the terrain of grapevine cultivation) and published his findings in two papers in 2000 under the titles “Wine and geography” and “Geology of the wine regions in Hungary”. Recently he and his co-workers had been engaged in the characterization of Hungarian Wine Terroirs. In addition to basic research, Professor Nagymarosy was extremely interested in practical aspects of wine geology, particularly in the role of pedology influencing the quality parameters and the organoleptic properties of wines.

Professor Nagymarosy was an excellent, professional musician, who was capable of playing music on fifteen different instruments.

He played the double bass in the folk-music group "Kalamajka" he founded and led at the Folk-Music Hall in Budapest every Saturday evening for 35 years continuously. He published 9 albums at the Hungarian Folk-Music Publishing House.

Together with the great musician and folk music expert Béla Halmos he travelled around the historic Hungarian regions of the Carpathian Basin and collected folk music from these areas.

In 2016 he was awarded with the Knight Order of Merit by the Hungarian Government.

After his death, many are grieving for the loss of a truly good friend and an excellent scientist.

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